

18th DEMSEE Annual Congress

PROGRAMME

Deregulated Electricity Market Issues in South-Eastern Europe

DATES June 22-23, 2026	VENUE Volgina 15, Belgrade, Serbia Mihajlo Pupin Institute	UNDER THE AEGIS OF The Region of Crete
REGISTRATION By email: info@demsee.org On-site confirmation: June 22, 2026, 09:00–10:00	WEBSITE www.demsee.org	CONTACT info@demsee.org

DAY 1 - MONDAY, JUNE 22, 2026

TIME	PROGRAMME
09:00-10:00	Registration
10:00-10:30	Opening Ceremony
10:30-12:00	Invited / Keynote Presentations
12:00-14:00	Lunch Break
14:00-16:00	Academic Paper Presentations
16:00-16:15	Closing Remarks / End of Day 1 Programme

OPENING CEREMONY

Opening and Welcome Address by Professor Thales Papazoglou, Founder of the DEMSEE Congress, and Igor Bundalo, Chairman of the 18th DEMSEE Congress.

INVITED / KEYNOTE PRESENTATIONS

10:30-12:00

Engineering-Grade Digital Twins: Unlocking Capacity, Resilience, and Smarter Investment

Valentina Loisi, Head of Commercial Strategy, Neara

Application of Artificial Intelligence in Power Systems

Prof. Mileta Žarković, University of Belgrade - School of Electrical Engineering

History of Frequency Control in Serbian Power System

Nikola Obradović, Corporate Director for International and Regulatory Affairs, EMS AD

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ACADEMIC PAPER PRESENTATIONS

14:00-16:00

No.	Paper Title	Authors
1	Validation of the System Split Application through Sandbox Testing	Igor Bundalo, Goran Jakupović, Marija Popović, Srđan Subotić, Andrijana Prešić, Kristina Janošević, Predrag Simić
2	Coordinated Security Analyses Enhancement Based on Western Balkans Power System Events	Jovana Jevremović, Ksenija Papić, Anđela Krljaš, Tijana Milovanović
3	Application of Genetic Algorithm (GA) for Generating Unit Selection at the Perucica HPP	Radomir Stamatović, Gojko Blagojević, Predrag Ilić, Milena Kruljević, Marija Savić
4	With the Crete Interconnection in Operation, Is There Still Room for New Renewable Energy Plants in Crete?	Hemmat Safwat
5	Joint Control of Active Power with Dual Operating Modes for the HPP Perucica	Milan Josifović, Goran Jakupović, Đorđe Koprivica, Gordan Konečni, Radomir Stamatović, Nebojša Panjevac

DAY 2 - TUESDAY, JUNE 23, 2026

TIME	PROGRAMME
10:00-10:30	Presentation of the European STUNNED Project
10:30-11:30	Visit to the Mihajlo Pupin Institute
11:30-12:00	Informal Discussion and Closing Remarks

Registration is required by email at info@demsee.org. Participation is free of charge, but the number of seats is limited.

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